

5. An illustrative application of the auralisation tool SCAuT

5.1. Introduction

The tool described in chapter 4 can be used to auralise many different scenarios. To test the potential of the tool and to use the tool to evaluate test subject perceptions of the street canyon, two series of tests were carried out: (a) preference tests and (b) a realism test.

In the first series (preference tests), two different situations were considered: (i) uniform façade and (ii) varying façade. In the uniform façade group (group i), the effect of the following cases were evaluated: (1) a listener on the street with the façades absorptive, diffusive or smooth, and (2) listeners at two different levels on a central, vertical plane with different uniform façade designs. In the group with varied façades along the canyon (group ii), we evaluated the effect of varying the placement of the listener along the canyon.

In the second series (realism tests), the effects of path discretisation length on the auralisation were evaluated. These tests will be described in detail in this section.

Preference tests were performed before realism tests because during an initial participation of trial subjects it was observed that the subjects would become critical of the quality of the auralisations once they had evaluated their realism. We did not want their experience of the realism test to affect their responses to the preference tests.

The listening tests were created on the web page <https://golisten.ucd.ie>. Test subjects were asked to listen to the auralisations using headphones or earphones. The questions in these tests used the MUSHRA and ACR methods described below (Barry et al., 2021).

5.1.1. Multiple Stimuli with Hidden Reference and Anchor (MUSHRA)

This type of test is used to evaluate the relative quality of multiple sound files by assigning each a score between 0 and 100 from a continuous scale. The questions for tests 1 and 4 described in this chapter are based on this approach.

5.1.2. Absolute Category Rating (ACR)

This type of test is used to evaluate the quality of a sound file by assigning it a whole-number score from 1 to 5. Questions in tests 2 and 3 in this chapter are designed using this method.

5.2. Post-processing and preparation for listening tests

Prior to the creation of the listening tests, the auralisation files went through a preparation phase after being output from the auralisation tool. The first step was to amplify each file to ensure a strong enough playback volume in the subjects' devices.

The second post-processing process was to add fade-in and fade-out effects at the beginning and the end of each file, respectively. First, each auralisation file was cut to exactly 6.0 seconds while making sure that no audible data was affected. Then, the first second of each file was faded in and the final second of each file was faded out. These fading effects were done using the free software Audacity. Figure 5.1 shows the waveform of a stereo auralisation file that has been edited and that is ready for playback in the listening test.

Figure 5.1. Waveform of the edited auralisation file. Image from Audacity.

5.3. Preference tests

Three of the four tests evaluated the level of annoyance experienced by a person listening to the auralisations of various street canyon scenarios. These tests are described in the following sections.

5.3.1. Test 1: Listener at pedestrian level in a simple canyon with a uniform façade

This case addressed three simplistic scenarios that had no variation along the street canyon. The location of the receiver had y -coordinate 50 m, which represents half the canyon's length. The scenarios are as follows:

a. Absorptive

In this scenario, a relatively absorptive material was assumed to cover all the façade surfaces throughout the canyon. For this case, the absorption coefficients of a green wall provided in Azkorra et al. (2015) were used: 0.5, 0.4, 0.36, 0.37, 0.45, 0.5, 0.55, 0.6, and 0.65 at 62.5 Hz, 125 Hz, 250 Hz, 500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, 4 kHz, 8 kHz, and 16 kHz respectively. Diffusivity factors 0.5, 0.6, 0.6, 0.7, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 0.9, and 0.9 were used at the above frequencies. The absorption coefficient at frequencies lower than the hybrid cross-over frequency was neglected. That is, the FDTD impulse response from the specular case was hybridised with the impulse responses obtained from ray tracing.

Figure 5.2. The street canyon with absorptive walls along its length.

b. Diffuse reflective

In this scenario the façade structures have been selected to be ideally diffusive. In this case, absorption coefficients were set to zero and diffusivity factors were set to one for ray tracing. Figure 5.3 shows this geometry, which is inspired by the Schröder diffuser structure (Kowalczyk, 2008).

Figure 5.3. The street canyon with diffuse reflection properties. The structure of the façade is based on the Schröder diffuser (see Appendix B).

c. Specular reflective

In this case it is assumed that the building façades along the canyon are formed by two completely flat surfaces which are fully reflective. In this case, absorption coefficients and diffusivity factors were set to zero for ray tracing. Figure 5.4 shows this scenario.

Figure 5.4. The street canyon with smooth façade surfaces that create specular reflections.

Three auralisations were presented to each participant using the MUSHRA method. The questions were randomised for each test subject. The subjects were asked to assign an annoyance score to each of the three auralisations per the MUSHRA method. Figure 5.5 shows the interface for this question.

Figure 5.5. The MUSHRA interface for test 1

The purpose of this test was to study the effect of extreme façade design conditions on the aural perception of a pedestrian. Event levels expressed in dB(A) were calculated from wave file data. These levels are to be understood with respect to full scale in the wave file, so the levels allow for a comparison between the stimuli. The values do not describe the absolute levels that did depend on the reproduction volume with each participant. A-weighting was applied to mimic the frequency dependent sensitivity of the human ear. Table 5.1 shows these levels.

Table 5.1. The event levels and maximum levels in dB(A) for test 1 auralisations

Façade type	Event level dB(A)	Max level dB(A)
Absorptive	-23.4	-26.1
Diffuse	-19.0	-21.4
Specular	-21.6	-24.8

5.3.2. Test 2: Effects of elevation and façade type

In this test, the effects of elevation and façade type on the preference of the listener were evaluated.

Figure 5.6. The two different receiver positions (blue) and the car path (red) for test 2

Six auralisation files were presented to the test subjects. Three considered the listener at point (E) at an elevation of six meters, and three considered the listener at point (F) at an elevation of nine meters. The three different auralisations at each point represented the three different façade types. The subjects were asked to evaluate their annoyance in six separate questions following the ACR method. The questions were randomised for the participant. The interface for each of the six auralisation tests is shown in figure 5.7.

Figure 5.7. The ACR interface for each question in test 2

The purpose of this test was to study the effect of listener elevation and façade design on annoyance. This type of study can be used to understand which building stories would be affected most by a change in the façade design. Event levels expressed in dB(A) were calculated from wave file data and are given in table 5.2. It can be seen that compared to point E, the levels at point F are generally lower which is expected due to the larger distance to the source.

Table 5.2. The event levels and maximum levels in dB(A) for test 2 auralisations

Point	Façade type	Event level dB(A)	Max level dB(A)
E	Absorptive	-30.5	-33.9
	Diffuse	-26.0	-29.3
	Specular	-28.2	-31.8
F	Absorptive	-31.7	-35.0
	Diffuse	-27.5	-31.0
	Specular	-28.5	-31.9

5.3.3. Test 3: Effect of location along a canyon with varying façades

In this scenario the pass by is auralised for three different pedestrian locations along a street canyon with a varying façade.

Figure 5.8. The street canyon with varying façades. The car passes by different façade situations including smooth surfaces, a gap, and diffusive surfaces. Three listener positions are set for creating the auralisations: (1) in front of the smooth façade (point A), (2) in front of the gap between the buildings (point B), and (3) in front of the diffusive façade (point C).

In this case three auralisations were presented to the subjects. Figure 5.8 shows receiver locations at points A, B, and C, which respectively lie between flat façades, building gaps, and diffusive façades. The subjects were asked to evaluate the annoyance level by answering three separate ACR-type questions. The order of the auralisations was randomised.

The interface was similar to the one shown in figure 5.7. The aim of this test was to figure out if there are significant differences between the levels of annoyance experienced under the three different facade conditions along the street. The signal levels are shown in table 5.3.

Table 5.3. The event levels and maximum levels in dB(A) for test 3 auralisations

Point	Event level dB(A)	Max level dB(A)
A	-24.3	-25.5
B	-27.3	-31.1
C	-20.0	-21.8

5.4. Test 4: Realism

In this test, four different auralisations were presented. They were obtained from a discretisation of the car path into segments of length 1, 0.5, 0.2, and 0.1 meters. The subjects were asked to evaluate the realism of the auralisations using the MUSHRA method. The order of questions was randomised as in the previous tests. The interface for this test is shown in figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9. The MUSHRA interface for test 4

The purpose of this test was to discover whether listeners would perceive a difference in realism between the auralisations created at the four different levels of precision. The realism of auralisations based on the discretisation lengths of 4 m and 2 m had already been evaluated to be unrealistic. The discretisation lengths were therefore chosen to be one metre or less. This is important as it directly affects the computation expense and, consequently, the simulation times as shown in table 5.4.

For this test, the geometry scenario consists of the ground only as shown in figure 5.11.

Figure 5.10. The blue sphere represents the receiver at 50 m, 14.5 m and 1.5 m. The red spheres represent typical discretised source path points. The four different simulation distancing choices are 0.1 m, 0.2 m, 0.5 m and 1.0 m.

The elapsed times for the ray tracing simulations with different discretisation lengths are shown in table 5.4. The hardware used for these simulations was a Lenovo laptop with an intel Core i5-6200U CPU with 2 cores and 4 threads, and a RAM of 16 GB.

Table 5.4. Ray Tracing and auralisation simulations elapsed times

dx (m)	Number of point sources	Elapsed time (hh:mm:ss)		
		Ray Tracing	Auralisation	Total
1.0	81	08:56:24	02:20:24	11:16:48
0.5	161	16:04:48	02:27:48	18:32:36
0.2	401	32:01:12	02:25:12	34:26:24
0.1	801	54:49:12	02:27:36	57:16:48

The event levels are shown in table 5.5.

Table 5.5. The event levels and maximum levels in dB(A) for test 2 auralisations

Δx (m)	Event level dB(A)	Max level dB(A)
0.1	-27.4	-29.4
0.2	-27.4	-29.3
0.5	-27.4	-29.3
1.0	-27.4	-29.3

5.5. Sound reproduction

Since the auralisation tool is to be used by designers in offices, it is expected that the files will be listened to through headphones. That's why effort was made to ensure that the test participants had access to headphones.

Besides, the questions the subjects were asked were comparative questions to evaluate preference or difference in perception of realism. Therefore the stereophonic reproduction of sound through headphones was considered acceptable. However, in order to perform calibrated tests with absolute sound pressure levels, it is necessary to perform in-ear sound pressure measurements or to conduct the tests in an immersive lab.

5.6. Test subjects

Twenty participants attended the tests. This number was selected as an appropriate number lying in the 16-32 range recommended by Nordtest Method (2002). The 20 participants were located in 20 different countries. Participants declared that they had access to headphones. Of the 20 participants, five were female and 15 were male. Ten participants were in the age range 25-34, six participants were in the age range 18-24, three were in the range 35-44, and one was in the range 45-54.

5.7. Results and discussion

5.7.1. Test 1

In order to establish whether there are differences in the data collected from annoyance as a function of façade types, it was decided to perform an ANOVA test. Data was collected at the interval level, and variation was estimated from the data. The independent variable is nominal with three levels (Absorptive, Diffuse and Specular) and the dependent variable (Annoyance) was numerical.

In the following tables there are three types of statistical descriptors:

1. Those of central tendency that indicate how the data tend to centre around a single value. The mean is the value that represents the central tendency, the median is the value that divides the sample into two equal groups (in quantity) and the mode refers to the most common value measured in the sample.

2. Those of dispersion, in this case, the standard deviation (SD) refers to how much the data is dispersed around the mean.

3. Those of distribution, such as skewness that refers to how symmetrical the shape of the distribution is, in this case values close to zero imply a fairly balanced distribution that is not skewed but is rather centralised.

The analyses have been done on the open source statistics platform Jamovi, available at <https://www.jamovi.org>.

Descriptive analyses of the data are shown in table 5.6. It is observed that the means and the respective medians differ by less than three points and that the asymmetry values are around zero. The greatest mean is seen to occur with the Diffuse façade type.

Table 5.6. Descriptors

	Façade type	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Skewness	
						Skewness	SE
Annoyance	Absorptive	28.1	27.0	0.0	21.8	0.686	0.512
	Diffuse	52.9	57.0	78.0 ^a	30.9	-0.168	0.512
	Specular	38.0	40.0	0.0 ^a	22.8	0.301	0.512

^a More than one mode exists, but only the first is reported

The box-and-whisker plot given in figure 5.11 more clearly shows the differences in the averages, especially in the type of façade mentioned (Diffuse).

Figure 5.11. Box-and-whisker plot comparison of façade types

Two outliers are observed: subject 14 in the absorptive case and subject 43 in the specular case. However, the asymmetry around zero seems to indicate that the mean was not particularly affected by such an aspect. We therefore decided to keep the original data for use in the subsequent statistical tests.

Figure 5.12 presents the distribution of data collected for each façade type. Despite the bimodality observed in the Diffuse façade case, the apparent normality supports subsequent parametric testing.

Figure 5.12. Distribution of the data collected for each façade type

Initially, the statistical assumptions of homoscedasticity and normality in the data sets were evaluated. Such assumptions are necessary to consider the strength of the parametric test considered.

Regarding homoscedasticity, table 5.7 shows that the p-values exceed 0.05, which indicates that there are no differences between the variances of the data groups considered. This satisfies one of the preconditions for the use of parametric tests such as ANOVA. The term “df” refers to degrees of freedom that is understood as the data that are free to vary when calculating a statistical test. Its interpretation is not necessary for the hypotheses being tested.

Table 5.7. Homogeneity of variances tests

	Statistic	df	df2	p
Levene's	3.03	2	57	0.056
Bartlett's	2.86	2		0.239

As for normality, table 5.8 shows that the p-values of the 3 tests considered (Shapiro-Wilk, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Anderson-Darling) exceed 0.05, which means that the theoretical normal distribution does not differ from the distribution of the data. It is assumed, then, that the data are normally distributed. Thus, the second precondition for the use of parametric tests is also satisfied.

Table 5.8. Normality tests

	statistic	p
Shapiro-Wilk	0.981	0.463
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.0840	0.792
Anderson-Darling	0.392	0.369

The p-value of 0.012 is lower than 0.05, which implies that there are significant differences between the three groups of data. An effect size of 0.144 is observed.

Table 5.9. ANOVA - Annoyance

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2
Façade type	6254	2	3127	4.81	0.012	0.144
Residuals	37030	57	650			

Since significant differences were found in the ANOVA, we proceeded with a post hoc test. Post hoc comparisons are statistical tests performed after obtaining a significant value of F that indicate which means are significantly different (King et al., 2018). Table 5.10 shows a p-value (Tukey) of 0.009 for the comparison of means between the Diffuse and Absorptive façade cases. The other possible comparisons were not significant. The quantities used are the t-test, Tukey's p-value and Cohen's d (King et al., 2018).

Table 5.10. Post hoc comparisons - Façade type

Comparison							
Façade type	Façade type	Mean Difference	SE	df	t	p_{tukey}	Cohen's d
Absorptive	- Diffuse	-24.9	8.06	57.0	-3.08	0.009	-0.975
	- Specular	-10.0	8.06	57.0	-1.24	0.434	-0.392
Diffuse	- Specular	14.8	8.06	57.0	1.84	0.165	0.583

Note: Comparisons are based on estimated marginal means

5.7.2. Test 2

In this test, the preferences of the experimental subjects were obtained for each facade as heard from two different elevations. Since the data collected corresponds to an ordinal level instead of a continuous variable, it was amenable to analysis using the Mann-Whitney U test, which is a non-parametric alternative to Student's t-test.

Table 5.11. Mann-Whitney U Test

		Statistic	p
Preferences in Absorptive	Mann-Whitney U	152	0.175

Table 5.11 shows a p-value of 0.175. This value is greater than 0.05, which implies that there is no significant difference between the preferences of the subjects with regard to elevation (6 m and 9 m) in the Absorptive case.

Figure 5.13. Comparison of 6 m and 9 m for the absorptive façade

Considering that the scale in Figure 5.13 only ranges from 3.0 to 3.5, we see that the differences are not very significant. Table 5.12 shows a p-value of 0.162. This value is greater than 0.05, which means that there is no significant difference between the preferences of the subjects according to the elevation (6 m and 9 m) in the Diffusive case.

Table 5.12. Mann-Whitney U Test

		Statistic	p
Preferences in Diffusive	Mann-Whitney U	152	0.162

Figure 5.14. Comparison 6 m and 9 m in diffusive façade

The scale in Figure 5.14 only ranges from 3.0 to 3.4, so, as in the previous case, we see that the differences are not very significant. Table 5.13 shows a p-value of 0.736. This value is greater than 0.05, which means that there is no significant difference between the preferences of the subjects with regard to elevation in the Specular case.

Table 5.13: Mann-Whitney U Test

		Statistic	p
Preferences in Specular	Mann-Whitney U	188	0.736

Figure 5.15. Comparison 6 m and 9 m in Specular façade

To evaluate whether there are differences with regard to façade type (Absorptive, Diffusive and Specular) in each elevation case (6 m and 9 m), an analysis was carried out using the Kruskal Wallis test. This ranks test is the non-parametric equivalent of the one-way ANOVA. It allows us to test the potential difference among independent groups when normality assumptions are violated. This is done by comparing the mean ranks across groups. Chi-squared (χ^2) is an indication statistical significance (Ryan, 2021).

Table 5.14. Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p
Preferences in 6 m	3.30	2	0.192

Table 5.14 shows that the p-value obtained is 0.192. This value is above 0.05, which means that there are no significant differences between the groups with regard to façade type in the case of 6 m elevation. Figure 5.16 shows that the distributions are indeed similar, which supports the claim that there are no differences between the groups.

Figure 5.16. Comparison of façade type for 6 m elevation

Table 5.15 shows that the p-value obtained is 0.818. This value is above 0.05, which means that there are no significant differences between the groups with regard to façade type in the 9 m elevation case.

Table 5.15. Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p
Preferences in 9 m	0.403	2	0.818

Figure 5.17 shows that the distributions are indeed similar, which supports the claim that there are no differences between the groups.

Figure 5.17. Comparison of façade type for 9 m elevation

5.7.3. Test 3

The Kruskal-Wallis test is a nonparametric test that takes range into account and that can be used to determine whether there are statistically relevant differences between two or more groups. The test determines whether the medians of the groups tested are different. In our case, the data are ordinal (between 1 and 5), so it is not possible to address characteristics such as normality that depend on a continuous distribution.

Table 5.16 shows that the Kruskal Wallis test p-value is 0.928, which is well above 0.05. This implies that there are no statistically significant differences between the groups. Epsilon-squared (ϵ^2) is a measure of effect size for the Kruskal–Wallis test (King et al., 2018).

Table 5.16. Kruskal-Wallis

	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2
Preference	0.149	2	0.928	0.00252

Figure 5.18 shows that the distributions are very similar, which corroborates the hypothesis that the data correspond to the same population.

Figure 5.18. Distribution of the data collected for each point (A, B, C)

5.7.4. Test 4

In order to identify differences in the realism data, an ANOVA test was performed. Data was collected at the interval level, and variation was estimated from the data. The independent variable (Car path discretisation length) is nominal with four levels (0.2, 0.5, 0.1 and 1.0) and the dependent variable (Perceived realism) was numerical.

Table 5.17. Descriptors

	Car path discretisation length (m)	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Skewness	
						Skewness	SE
Perceived realism	0.2	37.5	37.5	0.00 ^a	26.0	0.625	0.512
	0.5	41.9	39.5	0.00 ^a	29.8	0.717	0.512
	0.1	39.9	37.5	0.00 ^a	25.5	0.631	0.512
	1.0	51.0	54.0	0.00 ^a	26.9	-0.437	0.512

^a More than one mode exists, but only the first is reported

The descriptive analyses of the data is presented in table 5.17. It can be observed that the means and the respective medians are close to each other with less than 4 points difference. The skewness values are around zero. The highest mean is for the 1.0 m category and differs from the others by between 10 and 14 points.

Figure 5.19. Box-and-whisker plot comparing perceived realism

Five outliers are observed: subjects 33 and 21 in the 0.5 m case, subject 53 in the 0.1 m case, and subjects 70 and 76 in the 1.0 m case. However, the asymmetry around zero seems to indicate that the mean was not particularly affected by such an aspect. We therefore decided to keep the original data for use in the following statistical tests.

Figure 5.20. Distribution of the data collected for each car path discretisation length (m)

Figure 5.20 presents the distribution of data. It can be seen that the assumption of normality is met, and this allows us to proceed with parametric testing.

Initially, the statistical assumptions of homoscedasticity and normality in the data sets were evaluated. These characteristics are preconditions for the use of parametric tests. Regarding homoscedasticity, table 5.18 shows that the p-values exceed 0.05, which means that there are no differences between the variances of the data groups considered. We thus satisfy the first precondition for the use of ANOVA.

Table 5.18. Homogeneity of variance tests

	Statistic	df	df2	p
Levene's	0.0987	3	76	0.961
Bartlett's	0.566	3		0.904

As for normality, table 5.19 shows that the p-values of the 3 tests considered (Shapiro-Wilk, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Anderson-Darling) exceed 0.05, which means that the theoretical normal distribution does not differ from the distribution of the data. It is assumed, then, that the data are normally distributed. We thus satisfy the second precondition for the use of ANOVA.

Table 5.19. Normality tests

	statistic	p
Shapiro-Wilk	0.977	0.162
Kolmogorov-Smirnov	0.0681	0.852
Anderson-Darling	0.437	0.289

Having shown the use of parametric tests is appropriate, the results of our ANOVA test is given in table 5.20. A p-value of 0.421 implies that there are no significant differences between the four groups of data. In this table, η^2 gives an estimate of the strength of association between the independent and dependent variables. The F ratio is an indicator of the effect size; the closer to 1 it is, the smaller the effect size is (King et al., 2018).

Table 5.20. ANOVA - Realism

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2
Sound Type	2092	3	697	0.949	0.421	0.036
Residuals	55849	76	735			

5.8. Conclusions

In test 1, auralisations of a car pass-by in three different street canyon scenarios were evaluated for annoyance. The diffuse acoustic field in the canyon was shown to create the highest levels of annoyance. This annoyance was significantly greater than that in the case of the absorptive facade but not much different from that in the case of the specular reflective façade. One reason for the high level of annoyance in the diffuse scenario could be the high sound pressure levels in the auralisation compared to that in the other two scenarios as shown in table 5.1. The overall event level of the diffuse case auralisation was higher than the absorptive case by 4.4 dB and higher than the specular case by 2.6 dB. The maximum event level of the diffuse case auralisation was higher than the absorptive case by 4.7 dB and higher than the specular case by 3.4 dB.

However, the distribution in Figure 5.12 suggests that participants fall into two distinct groups when evaluating annoyance in the diffuse scenario. This may suggest that there are two types of listeners. One might find the pass-by in the diffuse scenario annoying due to the high sound pressure level. The other might have found the diffuse scenario less annoying due to its

relatively smooth build up and decay of acoustic energy. These hypotheses are interesting but need more investigation.

In test 2, two different listener elevations were tested against three different façade scenarios. Statistical analysis showed no significant difference in preference between the six situations. The purpose of this test was to show how the auralisation tool can be used to evaluate the preference of acoustics as experienced from certain building elevations (e.g. on balconies). The reason no significant difference was found might be that the tested facades were simplified so as to include only one vertical plate. In addition, the sound pressure level differences between auralisations at points E and F are in the order of 1 dB which is considered to be below the just audible level difference. To get more realistic results, it is suggested that more complex geometries involving balconies or other facade structures be examined. This would help by adding more reflections to the simulations, which would make the sounds more true to life.

In test 3, three different positions with respect to façade variations were considered for a hypothetical pedestrian along the street canyon: point A between flat walls, point B between building block gaps, and point C between diffusive façades. The statistical analysis again showed no significant difference between the perceived annoyances. The hypothesis was that the annoyance between the flat walls would be higher than that in the two other situations, but this did not prove to be the case. Similar situations can be generated, though, in which more sophisticated facade structures would accentuate the difference in effect on late reflections. Another possibility may be that the 5-point ACR scale was too coarse for the annoyance differences. A 11-point scale may be preferred for future similar tests.

In test 4, the perceived realism of four auralisation files was compared. The auralisations represented a car pass-by on a ground-only simulation geometry with four different resolutions: 0.1 m, 0.2 m, 0.5 m, and 1.0 m. Analysis showed no statistically significant difference between the perceived realism associated with these pass-bys. This means that there is no need to perform simulations with path discretisation smaller than 1.0 m. As suggested by table 5.4, this information helps save simulation time.